

Unmasking a Nollywood Auteur: Kabat Esosa Egbon's Embattled-Character Techniques in Selected Films

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Abstract

Since its evolution, academic interest has rapidly grown in the Nigerian popular culture; Nollywood. Film scholars have made concerted efforts to either develop new film theories which will be peculiar to the atypical Nollywood industry or to contextualize the existing universal film theories towards the study of Nollywood films. The contextualization of auteur (author) theory, a universal film theory in the study of Nollywood film culture is one of those laudable efforts by film scholars. In this light, various attempts by many film scholars in Nollywood to examine selected Nollywood directors such as Teco Benson, Tunde Kelani, Izu Ojukwu, Kunle Afolayan, Dickson Iroegbu, Obi Emelonye have seemingly been efficacious. Following the successful contextualization of auteur theory to Nollywood studies, it is therefore imperative to identify more Nollywood auteur-directors by extensively studying the overriding unique features across their films. This paper therefore attempts to unmask another Nollywood auteur-director through the application of Andrew Sarris's auteurial principles as a theoretical framework to understudy three randomly selected films of Kabat Esosa Egbon. This study therefore underpins his key auteurial feature which is referred by this paper as the *embattled-character* technique. It concludes that like every auteur-director, his embattled-character construct will often make audience recognize his films without necessarily seeing his name on the credit list.

Keywords: Nollywood, Auteur Theory, Kabat Esosa Egbon, key auteurial feature

Résumé

Depuis l'évolution de Nollywood, l'intérêt académique dans la culture populaire nigériane s'est rapidement développé. Les spécialistes du cinéma ont déployé des efforts concertés en vue du développement de nouvelles théories cinématographiques qui seront propres à l'industrie cinématographique de Nollywood ou pour la contextualisation des théories cinématographiques universelles existantes visant l'étude des films en provenance de Nollywood. La contextualisation de la théorie de l'auteur, une théorie cinématographique universelle dans l'étude de la culture cinématographique de Nollywood constitue l'un des efforts louables des spécialistes du cinéma. Dans cette optique, plusieurs tentatives de nombreux spécialistes de Nollywood qui étudient les travaux de certains réalisateurs de Nollywood comme Teco Benson, Tunde Kelani, Izu Ojukwu, Kunle Afolayan, Dickson Iroegbu et Obi Emelonye semblent être efficaces. Suite à la réussite dans contextualisation de la théorie de l'auteur aux études de Nollywood, il est donc impératif d'identifier davantage de metteurs en scène-auteurs de Nollywood tout en analysant de manière approfondie les caractéristiques particulières et prépondérantes dans leurs films. Cet article tente donc de démasquer un autre metteur en scène-auteur de Nollywood à travers l'application des principes d'Andrew Sarris comme cadre théorique aux fins d'analyser trois films de Kabat Esosa Egbon, choisis au hasard. Cette étude cerne donc son style clé d'auteur

qui est désigné par le présent article comme la technique du personnage en détresse. L'article note en guise de conclusion que, comme tout metteur en scène-auteur, son concept de personnage en détresse ferait souvent que le public reconnaisse ses films sans que son nom figure nécessairement sur la liste de personnes à reconnaître.

Mots-clés: Nollywood, théorie de l'auteur, Kabat Esosa Egbon, Style clé

Introduction

Film directing involves the creation of required dramatic beats as well as the composition of shots which aid the narration of a story. This is generally referred to as *mise-en-scene*. Over the years, many directors such as Alfred Hitchcock, Ingma Bergman, Robert Bresson, Luis Burnuel, Michelangelo Antonioni, Federico Fellini, and many others have employed different techniques (*mise-en-scene* attributes) towards ensuring that filmic stories are well received by the audience. The application of these various *mise-en-scene* techniques by various directors has given rise to the evolution of distinct directorial styles. Thus, the distinguishing features of peculiar directorial styles are often seen in the unique ways in which various directors handle the *mise-en-scene* attributes in their films.

Nollywood has been described by scholars like Shaka, 2003; Uwah, 2013; Ayakoroma, 2014; Okwuowulu, 2018 as a child of circumstance. Thus, its filmic cultures and styles are seemingly peculiar when compared to the overriding filmic cultures in the world. Since its advent, many directorial styles and techniques have evolved gradually. It is instructive to note that at the inception of Nollywood, existing television directors in Nigerian Television Authority such as, Chris Obirapu, Chika Onu, Andy Amanechi, Ndubuisi Okoh and a few others readily provided the required directing manpower in the emergent video film industry. These directors who were previous staff of Nigerian Television Authority seemingly imposed television drama styles into Nollywood video film directing. Suffice it to mention that the existing television directorial styles are trajectories of stage directorial styles. Of course, during the monopoly period of NTA in the 1980s, before the explosion of the private television houses in the 1990s, theatre arts graduates provided the required manpower for the television drama units in the Nigerian Television Authority. This television manpower would in turn provide manpower for the emergent Nollywood industry.

With the advent and development of Nollywood, few directors such as Teco Benson, Izu Ojukwu, Tunde Kelani, Andy Amanechi, Kunle Ofunlanya, Tunde Kelani and a few others have been always identified as Nollywood auteur-directors in academic parlance. In a country which has more than four hundred registered members of Directors' Guild of Nigeria, this researcher strongly believes in the existence of more auteur-directors in Nollywood than have frequently provoked academic discourse. It is against this background that this paper attempts to underscore features in the films by Kabat Esosa Egbon which enlists him as one of Nollywood auteur directors.

Auteurial Styles in Nollywood

It is often difficult to unmask the unique style applied by a particular director. This is particularly problematic if the director does not screenplay most of his films. This is because, styles in filmmaking are often perceived to be universal due to its nature. David Bordwell and Christin Thompson's notion underscores this opinion. According to them:

the filmmaker makes certain technical choices and adheres to them throughout the film. Across the film, a filmmaker will characteristically use three-point lighting, or continuity editing, or diegetic sound. A few segments might stand out as varying from the film's normal usage but in general a film tends to rely on consistent usage of certain techniques. The film's style results from a combination of historical constraints and deliberate choice (2010: p. 390).

This emphasizes that though film appears to have a universal language, the slight (un)conscious deviations by directors in the application of various *mise-en-scene* techniques creates a film style.

In discussing directing style, David Bordwell and Christin Thompson call to mind the *German expressionism* style and a *Soviet montage* style which represent a group of filmmakers within a certain region (2010, p. 390). This underpins the prevailing universal film culture as a style on its own. Thus a director within the boundaries of a particular film culture can only carve a niche for himself within the confinement of that filmic culture. In the light of this, in the bid to decode peculiar directorial style of a particular director, serious studies are to be made to underline the unique structures across a good number of films by the director. On this basis, studies in structuralism are very pertinent to auteurial studies. Structuralism, according to Corrigan and White is:

an approach to linguistics and anthropology that, when extended to literary and filmic narrative, looks for common structures rather than originality. In the case of film, these common structures might be plots or characters that recur across works (2009, p. 467).

This supposes that studies in filmic structures focuses on calling attention to common indexes across a number of films. Often, when such overriding features are seen in a number of films by a particular director, the director is said to be an auteur-director. The auteur theory is therefore a theory that highlights the similarity in motifs of various films by a particular director. Recent studies in auteur theory often anchor its framework on structuralism.

Numerous studies have been carried out on the application of auteur theory in Nollywood. Scholars such as Chisimdi Ihentuge (2007), Ovunda Ihunwo (2009), Sylvia Okwuosa (2012), Charles Okwuowulu (2012, 2013, 2014 and 2016), Innocent Uwah and Charles Okwuowulu (2017) have made serious efforts to highlight Tecu Benson, Izu

Ojukwu, Obi Emelonye, Tunde Kelani and Dickson Iroegbu as auteur-directors in Nollywood. Uwah and Okwuowulu in conceptualizing auteur theory observe that it is an aspect of film scholarship that deals primarily with the nature of *mise-en-scene* construction by directors. The director is often considered a technician by this theory, thus as one invested with the role of using the camera as a literary author does in writing to tell a story (2017, p.3).

The development of auteur theory is traced to the French film culture in the 1950s. The concept of auteur was defined by the famous article of François Truffaut titled 'A Certain Tendency of French Cinema' which was published in *Cahier du Cinema* in 1954 (Okwuowulu, 2012, p. 216). According to Okwuowulu, the development of auteur theory is traced to the foundation led by Alexander Astruc and his camera pen analogy which sublimates the cinematic camera as a pen. Thus, the supposition that the director uses the camera as a writer would use a pen. Peter Wollen and Andrew Sarris are known to have contributed tremendously towards the development of auteur theory, particularly, Andrew Sarris whose instructive essay 'Towards a Theory of Film History' tried to underpin the undertones of auteur theory (2012, Pp. 216-218).

The application of the term 'auteur' was first done by Andrew Sarris in his article 'Notes in the Auteur Theory' where he enumerated the three concentric circles: The outer circle which is the technique, the inner circle being the interior meaning and the middle circle representing the personal style (1979, P. 663). These three elements constitute the main component of auteurism in film studies. Thus, for a director to be categorized as auteur, he must in addition to being technically competent, have an interior meaning and have evolved a particular style. This issue of style is where the *mise-en-scene* elements of the film come to play. While some directors evolve styles through the dramatic elements of the film which involves the kind of stories told by these directors as well as the kind of characters they develop, others stamp their authority through the use of cinematography which involves how shots are constructed to represent meaning.

Ihentuge, presumably the first scholar that attempted to contextualize auteur theory in Nollywood argues that the predicament of auteur theory is that the Nollywood film industry is striving to be firmly established; therefore, practitioners pay less attention to established theories (2007 p. IX). Citing Sarris and Bazin's conceptualization of auteurism, he points out five features an auteur director should possess before he is recognized as one. These are:

- (a) Repeated return to the same subject matter
- (b) Habitually address a particular psychological or moral theme
- (c) Employ a recurring style
- (d) Stick to a particular genre, or
- (e) Demonstrate any combination of the above (2007, p. 17).

Furthermore, his analysis of Benson's auteur techniques is based on Benson's thematic preoccupation which he asserts is poetically justified in his approach to societal ills (2007, p.51). His use of feminist and psychoanalytic theories to analyze Benson's characters and themes are apt as they bring out the underlying meanings in Benson's films. In addition, Ihentuge in another work, titled, "The auteur as a socio-political commentator: A reading of selected films of Teco Benson," foregrounds the ideological impact of Benson's films as a watchdog to the society. In his argument towards contextualizing auteur theory in Nollywood, he asserts that:

...the theory could be applied to any film industry irrespective of its stage of development. It will thus amount to great disservice to continue to deny Nollywood auteurial attentions. Not with its international high rating (2008 p. 212).

According to him, Benson began his action films with *The State of Emergency 1* (2000). After the production of *The State of Emergency 1*, he tried his hands on several genres and stuck to a particular genre.

Benson's commitment to change in the society was analyzed by Ihentuge in his (Benson) selected works such as *Mission to Nowhere* (2007) *Explosion* (2006) and *The Senator* (2003). He observes that these films are replete with the same moral issues and pointed out that the auteur uses *Explosion* to make a political statement about the corrupt and inefficient nature of Nigerian police (2008 p. 220). This according to him is seen in the detection of the murderer of Mr. Hopkins by a foreign security outfit. The analysis of ideology in Benson films is hinged on his use of film as social watch dog. Prior to the insecurity situation of *Boko Haram*, his first action film, *State of Emergency* predicted the agitation of a certain group of people to their country. Ihentuge notes that the theme of sociopolitical orientation reoccurs in Benson's films and therefore proposes his inclusion among the auteurial cadre of Nollywood (2008 p. 220).

On the other hand, Ovunda Ihunwo's work titled "Auteurist Versus *Metteur-en-scene* Directors: A Case Study of the Works of Dickson Iroegbu and Chika Onu" problematizes the practice of auteur in Nollywood. According to him, the action of the executive producers who dictate to directors is for economic reasons (2009, p. 4). Ihunwo situates Dickson Iroegbu as auteur and Chika Onu as a *metteur-en-scene* director. He notes that only independent directors who are not tied to the apron strings of the executive producers can freely practise auteurship in Nollywood. This according to him is as a result of the production indices in Nollywood which is controlled by the business merchant (2009, pp. 60-68). In his theoretical framework, he notes that Paul Watson presents a controversial theory of authorship which he terms: "the three paradoxes of cinematic authorship". He expounds that the first paradox is the "paradox of collaboration" which questions the plausibility of attributing authorship to a single creative source given the collaborative nature of filmmaking. The "paradox of theory" which he presents as the second illogicality of auteur theory questions the ideology of cinematic authorship. In addition, in the third paradox which he termed "the cultural paradox" he asserts that author discourse has

continued to present itself even at a time when many critics think that film theory has finally wriggled out of the fascination of the cinematic authorship (2009, pp. 16-17).

In her studies, Okwuosa equally problematizes the application of auteur theory in Nollywood. She agrees with Ihunwo that "...this concept is not generally followed in Nollywood due to the level of education/understanding of most executive producers" (2011, p.8). She affirms that these executive producers dictate the tempo of the film production process. In her opinion, the auteur theory exists in its infancy stage in Nollywood despite distractions from executive producers. Thus, the practitioners of authorship in Nollywood are oblivious of its theoretical principles. Carrying out an in-depth study on Izu Ojukwu's film motifs, she concludes that the emergence of independent directors will solve the problem. She argues for a total reorientation of major stakeholders in the industry for a perfect understanding of schedule and responsibilities of different crew offices (2011, p. 21). In reaction to Okwuosa's assertion, this paper observes that the emergence of Nollywood's independent directors will at best create auteur directors whose work may not be a commercial success. One cannot negate the indefatigable role of the marketing structure of the film marketers in the industry. What really makes a director an auteur is his ability to stamp his personality amidst the production circuit.

However, having acknowledged the technique-driven nature of auteurial analysis, Okwusa still bases her analysis on thematic preoccupation of Ojukwu's films. She did not give detailed analysis of Ojukwu's filmic motifs in analyzing his works. Thus she asserts that Ojukwu is inconsistent in motifs. According to her, "Izu Ojukwu cannot be said to have evolved a particular set of auteurial feature that cuts across all his films without modifications and alternations" (2011, p. 55). She goes ahead to identify the following as Ojukwu's auteurial features:

Repeated treatment of the some moral and psychological themes.
Repeated return to the same subject matter. Recurring style in his
shot to shot relations. Use of symbols, locations and battle scenes.
(2011, p. 55).

This paper applauds the features which she discovers about Ojukwu's auteurial techniques but disputes the notion that Ojukwu's auteurial features do not cut across his entire films. This is because Okwuosa's analysis is hinged on thematic than technique perspective. In her technical analysis, Okwuosa applauds Ojukwu's continuity editing. It is avowed that most film directors in Nollywood use continuity editing technique, therefore, plaudits on continuity editing merely gives credence to Ojukwu. Nevertheless, this researcher believes that Ojukwu's story lines may not have the same structural perspective; his *mise-en-scene* construction is very consistent, especially his silhouette shot description which recurs in all his film. He often uses this shot technique to foreground the anguish which his major character often passes through.

On another note, Nwafor believes that a director is an auteur if he makes final decisions on what is seen on the screen. He notes that the director's dominance has been seemingly accepted in different film cultures all over the world. He asserts that:

The earlier caption of "a film directed by Spike Lee" now reads "a Spike lee film" indicating a global acceptance of the place of the director as an auteur (2013, p. 75).

Observing the pitfall in the dominant nature of producer – director controversy as well as the notion that referring to a director as auteur often inflates his ego while diminishing that of other crew members, Nwafor argues that the documentarist who obviously works with less crew members is the real auteur (2013, p. 75). While this paper does not dispute this notion, it should be stressed that production process in a documentary film still involves an army of personnel just as in any feature film. It is rather the personality dominance and the recurring motifs rather than the number of production personnel involved that makes an auteur. Thus for a documentarist to be an auteur, the reoccurring features of an auteur must be evident in his various documentaries.

Okwuowulu in his studies titled: "Auteur theory and *mise-en-scene* Techniques: A study of selected Nollywood directors" conceptualizes three peculiar authorship practices in Nollywood. Citing Teco Benson, Izu Ojukwu and Tunde Kelani as models, the thesis proposes that Nollywood auteurs can be categorized based on their ideological, dramatic and technical penchants. While the auteurial interest of Kelani is focused on ideological authorship because of his seeming obsession with the Yoruba cultural heritage which he often portrays in his films, Teco Benson's films are propelled by the dramatic contents which is filled with high suspense motifs. Izu Ojukwu on the other hand can be said to be obsessed with the visual language in his films. This situates him as a technical auteur-director (2016, p.130-223). According to Okwuowulu:

In evaluating auteurial imprints of either the ideological, dramatic or the technical auteur practitioner, one should bear in mind that every narrative has a particular ideology it represents. On the other hand, every auteur director is so considered because he is technically competent. In addition, one should bear in mind that for the dramatic component of a film to make an immediate impression to the viewers before the technique means that every film is composed of dramatic element. Therefore, since these three components are seen in every film, a director must exhibit a high level of commitment for one of these categories before he is considered a practitioner of such (2016, p. 213).

Therefore, to define the category of any auteur-director, one needs to have screened a number of films by the same director over the years to establish his or her stylistic stand points.

Unmasking Kabat Esosa Egbon's Embattled-Character Techniques in Selected Films

Kabat Esosa Egbon, a great screenwriter as well as film director started his career from writing and veered into film directing. He is known to have screen-played the widely acclaimed *Igodo* (1999) an epic film that firmly established the epic film tradition in Nollywood. Some of the films he directed are: *A Love Story*, *Mama*, *No Strings Attached*, *The Guardian*, *Husbands of Lagos* to mention a few. A random sampling as well as analyses of three of his films: *A love Story*, *The Guardian* and *No Strings Attached* is undertaken in this paper to underpin his auteurial features.

No strings Attached presents three characters who struggle in different ways to break out from their emotional entrapments occasioned by their forlorn past experiences. The narrative presents a complicated plot struggle which features Kate (Belinda Efe), an accomplished career woman who struggles to break up her emotional state and settle with a man in marriage. Thus the narrative revolves around the relationship between three characters embattled by their antiquity. Kate's emotional state is often rekindled by her previous experience of sexual molestation by her elder brother. Conversely, Charles (Williams Uchemba) an orphan who finds himself in a sexual confinement with her mother's friend in a bade to complete his university education, currently struggles to break out from that relationship. Similarly, Peter (Kenneth Okolie) who has been emotionally unstable having lost his dear wife in an accident involving a reckless driver battles to find peace. The activities of these three characters embattled by their antiquity sustain the narrative.

In his film, *The Guardian*, Kabat foregrounds the life and the emotional embattlement of an assassin, Smoke (Daniel K. Daniel) who unleashes mayhem on the nation. Smoke's emotional state and the undisclosed reason for his act of assassination are used as deep suspense techniques in the film. The assassin finally unfolds to a fearless journalist (Yvonne Jegede Fawole) the remote causes of his emotional distress. He had been a police officer who had lost his wife and children. His family was murdered by politicians who were involved in the corruption cases he was investigating. Consequently, he resigns as a police officer and decides to kill those politicians in a vengeance to the death of his family. The narrative, is akin to the western model of an action film. It starts with the serial murder of the victims with the directorial intention of the murderer foreclosed. However, Smoke is later tormented spiritually by one of his victims, a pastor who prayed for him (Smoke) before she is murdered by Smoke. It is this inner struggle within Smoke which pushes him to tell his side of the story.

Kabat's film, *A Love story* chronicles the love life of Ida (Daniel Liyod) and Adaku (Jeniffer Uzoma) who shortly after their marriage discovers that they are both siblings. Before this unprecedented discovery, is engulfed in a deep emotional entrapment occasioned by his past life. Raised by a single mother who tells him his father is dead and realizing that his father is still alive, he leaves his mother in the village and goes in search of his father in Lagos. There in Lagos, he is homeless and stricken with poverty and he unconsciously gets himself involved in crime. Again, in search of self-concealment from his wife and the

viewers by extension, his character becomes queer, thus creating deep suspense in the narrative. He had denounced his mother before his marriage, reasons that is later revealed to be that she concealed his identity to him. Thus, the paradox of his mother's love towards Ida and Ida's repressed love and near-hatred towards his mother equally creates sufficient suspense in the narrative. After the prolonged emotional embattlement and cult guilt, Ida's lifestyle is discovered by his wife. Then, after serious battle to save his marriage, Ida discovers in a dramatic twist that Adaku, the wife she has married for some time now is his half-sister. Kabat's alienation techniques in this narrative are very commendable. This is because though Mama (Tina Mba), Ida's mother had told Ida a story of two siblings who got married and later discovered their genealogy, one could not predict that same fate will greet Ida owing to his questionable paternity.

From the foregoing analyses of three randomly selected Kabat's films, it is evident that Kabat's auteurial seal lies in his filmic characterization of sustaining his viewers through developing embattled characters. With intrinsic study of character structure rather than looking at his cinematographic expressions in his films, this auteurial motif is easily discernible. Of course, his cinematographic expressions are very apt. However, he is yet to evolve a unique cinematographic expression. This does not in any way make him less professional in his cinematographic expressions. It rather means that even though he has not developed any consistent cinematographic style which is peculiar in his films. However his peculiar character construct makes him an auteur director following the auteurial theoretical frameworks established in the course of this work.

Apart from the embattled characterizations in *No Strings Attached* and *The Guardian*, both present the lead characters to have lost their families: including their wives and children. This great loss aggravates their emotions. *A Love Story* equally presents characters that do not have stable families. The issues of broken home and unstable families are seeming a technique often employed by Kabat to unravel the emotions of his characters. He uses this technique to create adequate suspense that apparently sustains his narratives.

Conclusion

There is no easily recognizable cinematographic motif in Kabat Esosa's films. However, his auteurial seal is evident in the characterizations of his main characters who often possess similar characteristics. His major characters are often entrapped in an emotional struggle occasioned by their past bizarre experiences making them to behave in a queer manner. In these films, reasons for the odd attitude of the character are often foreclosed to the viewers in the inception of the narrative. This often creates high level of suspense.

Film scholars may misread Kabat Esosa as a *metteur-un-scene* director as he has not been seen to have developed a peculiar cinematographic style. Nevertheless, the application of auteur theoretical framework as well as structuralism in Kabat's three randomly selected films justifies his categorization by this study as an auteur-director. This underscores the peculiar motif in his character construct which is seen in most of his films. Following Okwuowulu's conceptualization of authorship categories in Nollywood, Kabat is categorized a dramatic auteur-director. This is because his auteurial imprint is seen on his filmic characters who are often embattled in an emotional trauma. This unique feature when

compared with Teco Benson, a director whose auteurial penchant equally falls into dramatic authorship, the distinction is very visible. Benson's characterization often focuses on the psychology of the victim of crime while Kabat's characterization often focuses on the psychology of the perpetrator crime or on a character perplexed by either his past mistakes or the present circumstances surrounding him/her. This creates Kabat's personal style and distinguishes from other auteur-directors. Like every auteur-director, his embattled character construct will often make the audience to recognize his films as his without seeing his name on the credit list.

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Filmography

- No Strings Attached* (2016) Dir: Kabat Esosa Egbon. Starring: Kenneth Okolie, Bellinda Effah, Sylvia Oluchi, Williams Uchemba, producer kabat Esosa Egbon. Executive producer – Rok Studio,
- A Love Story* (2017) Dir: Kabat Esosa Egbon; Producer; Kabat Esosa Egbon, Starring: Francis Duru, Tina Mba, Daniel Liyod and Jennifer Uzoma. Executive producer: Rok Studio.
- The Guardian* (2016) Dir: Kabat Esosa Egbon. Starring: Daniel K. Daniel and Yvonne Jegede Fawole Producer: Rok Studio.